

OUR MOTHERS ARE DYING: TIME SERIES ANALYSIS OF MACROECONOMIC VARIABLES AND MATERNAL HEALTH IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Our mothers are dying! This paper examined time series analysis of macroeconomic variables and maternal health in Nigeria using annual time series data covering a period of 35 years, which is between 1990 and 2024. The study used Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) as the dependent variable whereas Inflation (INF), Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC), Government Expenditure on Health (GEH), and Unemployment (UNEMP) were used as the independent variables. Data were collected from secondary sources and analyzed using descriptive statistics, unit root test, Co-integration and ECM modeling techniques. The results of the ECM show that Inflation (INF) increases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM); GDP per capita (GDPPC) reduces Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM); Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) reduces Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM); and Unemployment (UNEMP) increases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in Nigeria. The study therefore concluded that Inflation (INF) significantly increases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM), indicating that rising prices may reduce household access to essential healthcare and nutrition for our mothers and also negatively impacts maternal health services in Nigeria within the period of study. The study therefore recommended amongst others that in order to improve maternal health and consequently reduce maternal mortality in Nigeria, governments are required to initiate and implement effective macroeconomic policies aimed at controlling inflation in order to safeguard household consumption of essential goods and health services, thereby reducing inflation-induced maternal mortality.

Keywords: Time Series, Macroeconomic variables, Maternal Health, Maternal Mortality, Unit Root Test, Co-integration, Error Correction Model.

Introduction

Quality health constitutes a basic objective of development. It is a fundamental human right all over the world (Ezekwu, 2014). Health is recognized as an important aspect of human and economic development for both developing and developed countries. One's health affects the ability to participate in society, the work force, and to live a full and complete life. More specifically, the aspect of health that affects only women merits additional concern as this sector of the population has long been under cared for (Wheelock, 2023). The United Nations Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) from 2000 to 2015 and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) from 2015 to 2030 underscore the importance of good health for economic development and socioeconomic progress (Adegoke et al. 2022). In fact, one of the primary goals from the United Nations 17 Sustainable Development Goals is to reduce Maternal Mortality on a global scale. That is, after the importance of ending poverty and hunger, the UN has chosen "good health and wellbeing" as

the third goal. Thus, the first related goal under this overarching goal is “by 2030, reduce the global maternal mortality ratio to less than 70 per 100,000 live births (Wheelock, 2023).

According to Sajedinajad et al. (2015), maternal mortality is a specific, yet cumulative, way to view the healthcare system, quality of life, and advancement of society. Michelle Obama once observed: “that communities and countries and ultimately the world are only as strong as the health of their women” (Michelle Obama, 2009). The above highlights that maternal mortality matters at the most basic level because one should care when women die in our society; and it is expected that pregnancy should most often lead to life, not death (Wheelock, 2013). Hence, the phrase “Our mothers are dying” exposes the urgent maternal health crises in our societies, especially in Nigeria where the BBC once reported that “Nigeria is the world’s most dangerous nation in which to give birth” (BBC, 2025).

According to UNICEF (2025), from 2000 to 2023, the global maternal mortality ratio (MMR) declined by 40 percent - from 328 deaths to 197 deaths per 100,000 live births, based on UN inter-agency estimates. This translates into an average annual rate of reduction of 2.2 percent. Though there has been significant progress in reducing global maternal mortality ratio between 2000 and 2015, UNICEF noted that the numbers have been stagnant when averaging rates of reduction between 2016 and 2023.

However, a global report revealed that Nigeria has the highest estimated maternal death rate, accounting for over one-quarter (28.3%) of all estimated global maternal deaths, with approximately 8,200 maternal deaths, and a maternal mortality ratio of 1,047 per 100,000 live births (Dogbanya, 2025). This high number of maternal deaths in Nigeria reflects inequalities in access to quality health services and highlights the gap between rich and poor (WHO, 2025).

Several studies (Adegoke et al. 2022; Monstert, 2023; Mlambo et al. 2023; amongst others, have documented the impact of macroeconomic variables on maternal health. However, the full implication of macroeconomic variables and maternal health in Nigeria is yet to be exposed.

This study examined the impact of macroeconomic variables on maternal health in Nigeria. This study is motivated by two important factors. First studies have shown that Nigerian mothers show negligible interest in utilizing primary health care services even when the services are available, especially in the rural areas (Ezekwu, 2014). Secondly, reports have shown that Nigeria has the highest estimated maternal deaths rate and has been classified as the world’s most dangerous nation in which to give birth (BBC, 2025). It is therefore imperative to understand and analyze how macroeconomic variables impact on maternal health in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section covers theoretical literature, conceptual literature and empirical literature review.

Macroeconomic Variables

Macroeconomic variables refers to key indicators like Gross Domestic Product (GDP), inflation, and unemployment, used to gauge a nation’s overall economic health, alongside others like exchange rates, government expenditure, interest rates, exports, and imports.

Macroeconomic variables reflects aggregate production, price stability, and employment levels.

According to EconomicPoint (2026), macroeconomic variables are associated with economic aggregates: a country, a region, the population of a country, and all companies in a country.

Thus, some of the commonly used macroeconomic variables are, inflation, unemployment, Gross Domestic Product, Government spending, interest rate, and exchange rates. Macroeconomic variables are crucial for understanding and predicting the performance of an economy as they provide insights into the factors that drive economic growth, stability and well-being (Fiveable, 2025).

Maternal Health

Maternal health refers to the health of women during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period. According to (Fawke et al. (2021), maternal health refers to the health of an individual during pregnancy, delivery, and the post-partum period (also known as the puerperium, lasting approximately 6 weeks or 42 days after birth). However while the events of this span of time are often positive and fulfilling experiences, for too many this period is associated with suffering, ill health, and even death.

Maternal Mortality

According to UNICEF (2025), maternal mortality refers to deaths due to complications from pregnancy or childbirth. As noted by Dogbanya (2025), a global report revealed that Nigeria has the highest estimated maternal death rate, accounting for over one – Quarter (28.3%) of estimated global maternal deaths, with approximately 8,200 maternal deaths, and a material mortality ratio of 1,047 per 100,000 live births. The report further observed that with only 43% of births in Nigeria assisted by a skilled provider, only 39% of birth taking place in a health facility, and 59% delivered at home (National Population Commission, 2018).

Why Do Our Mothers Die?

Our mothers die as a result of consequential complications during and following pregnancy and childbirth. Most of these complications develop during pregnancy and most are preventable or treatable. Other complications may exist before pregnancy, but are worsen during pregnancy, especially if not managed as part of the woman’s care (WHO, 2025). According to Cresswell et al. (2009), the major complications that account for around 75% of all maternal deaths are:

- i. Severe bleeding (mostly bleeding after childbirth);
- ii. Infections (usually after childbirth);
- iii. High blood pressure during pregnancy (pre-eclampsia and eclampsia);
- iv. Complications from delivery; and
- v. Unsafe abortion.

Thus, the phrase “our mothers are dying” reflects deep grief, often from losing a mother, but also points to the global crisis of maternal mortality, where preventable deaths during pregnancy and childbirth remain alarming, especially in third world regions like sub-Saharan Africa.

Theoretical Literature Review

Mosley and Chen Theory of Child Survival in Developing Countries

The theoretical basis of this paper like in my previous papers is the Mosley and Chen (1984)

Theory of Child Survival in Developing Countries (Ezekwu & Igwe 2025; Ezekwu, 2026). Traditionally, social science research on child mortality has focused on the association between socio-economic status and levels and patterns of mortality in populations. Correlations between mortality and socioeconomic characteristics are used to generate causal inferences about the mortality determinants. Income and maternal education, for example are two commonly measured correlates (and inferred causal determinants) of child mortality in developing countries population (Mosley & Chen, 1984).

The theory of child survival in developing countries by Mosley and Chen (1984) proposes a new analytical framework for the study of the determinants of child survival in developing countries. The approach incorporates both social and biological variables and integrates research methods employed by social and medical scientists. It also provides for the measurement of morbidity and mortality in a single variable. The framework is based on the premise that all social and economic determinants of child mortality necessarily operate through a common set of biological mechanisms, or proximate determinants, to exert an impact on mortality. The framework according to Mosley & Chen (1984) is intended to advance research on social policy and medical interventions to improve child survival as shown in the diagram below.

Source: Mosley and Chen (1984)

From the diagram, the key to the theory is the identification of a set of proximate determinants or intermediate variables that directly influence the risk of morbidity and mortality. All social and economic determinants must operate through these variables to affect child survival. According to Mosely and Chen (1984), the proximate determinants are grouped into five categories:

- i. Maternal factors: age; parity; birth interval
 - ii. Environmental contamination: air, food/water/fingers; skin/soil/inanimate objects; insects' vectors
 - iii. Nutrient deficiency: calories; protein; micronutrients (vitamins and minerals).
 - iv. Injury: accidental; intentional.
 - v. Personal illness control: personal preventive measures; medical treatment.
- For this study, the theory of child survival is a useful indication that positive improvements in all the proximate determinants will positively affect mortality and morbidity thereby increasing the rate of child survival in Nigeria. A reduction

in environmental contamination and personal illness is needed to enhance child survival among under-five children improvement in maternal factors and nutritional deficiency is also needed to balance longevity among under-five children in Nigeria, all things being equal.

Empirical Literature

There exist a dearth of research on the association between macroeconomic variables and maternal and child mortality, particularly within the Nigerian context. Prior studies consistently underscore the indispensability of macroeconomic stability in achieving improved outcomes in maternal and child health. Adegoke et al. (2022) studied macroeconomic determinants, maternal and infant SDG targets in Nigeria: correlation and predictive modelling. The study examined the combined effect of health expenditure and other key macro-economic factors on health indices such as maternal and newborn and child mortality in Nigeria. The study used Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL), which is usually used for large T model and spans from 1995 to 2020. The results show a significant negative relationship between health outcomes and macro-economic determinants namely, household consumption, total health expenditure and gross fixed capital; and a significant positive relationship between health outcomes and unemployment.

Mlambo et al. (2023) carried out a study on determinants of maternal mortality in Southern Africa: a macro-level analysis. The study investigated the macro determinants of maternal mortality in Southern African Development Community (SADC) states. The study was quantitative, and it used secondary data to achieve its objective. A panel data estimation (Generalized Method of Moments) covering the period from 2005-2019 was used to examine how various factors affect maternal mortality. The result of the econometric analysis revealed that a significant positive impact of fertility, GDP per capita and HIV on maternal mortality. This implied that when fertility, GDP per capita and HIV are increasing, maternal mortality also increases. The result also showed that education has a negative relationship with maternal mortality. This implied that when literacy levels (education) increases, maternal mortality decreases.

Mostert (2023) studied macroeconomics and health: understanding the impact of a declining economy on health outcomes of children and young adults in South Africa. The study was designed to show how a declining economic state affects the mental health conditions, metabolic risk factors, communicable conditions, and non-communicable conditions of adolescent (18-year cohorts) and adult (25-year cohorts) population groups comparatively. The study utilized a panel analysis using secondary data issued by statistic South Africa. A two-stage Least Squared Model (2SLS) to quantify the impact of the declining economy on mental health conditions (depression and traumatic stress), non-communicable conditions (cancer and diabetes), metabolic risk factors (alcohol abuse and hypertension), and communicable conditions (influenza, diarrhea, dry cough) of both adolescent and young adult population groups. The results revealed that declining economic state of 2008-2014 worsens the mental health conditions, metabolic risk factors, and non-communicable conditions of adolescent and young adult populations. The results showed that the impact of the declining economy worsens mental health conditions, metabolic risk factors, and non-communicable conditions more in urban settings than in rural regions. Men abused alcohol

more than women during economic decline, triggering worsening mental health conditions, hypertension, and non-communicable conditions, especially in the adult population residing in urban settings.

Okeowo et al. (2025) studied maternal mortality in Nigeria and implications for economic development. The study used annual time series data spanning 33 observations from 1989 to 2022. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) served as the proxy for economic growth, which is the dependent variable, while fertility rate (FERATE), health expenditure (HEAEXP), and mortality rate (MMR) served as the exogenous variables. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test was used to determine the stationarity level of variables. The results showed that, in contrast to MMR and FERATE, which have negative relationships with the dependent variable (Gross Domestic Product), HEAEXP has a positive relationship with the dependent variable.

Patterkadaven & Qayed (2024) carried out a study on unravelling the dynamics of macroeconomic variables and infant mortality in India based on ARDL model analysis. The study examined the correlation between macroeconomic variables specifically GDP per capita, consumer price index (CPI), unemployment, and infant mortality in the Indian context. The analysis used secondary data procured from reputable sources such as the World Bank and Reserve Bank of India (RBI). The study employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lag

(ARDL) Error correction Model, which accounted for the interplay between the variables over time. The findings of the study established the existence of long-term cointegration between macroeconomic variables and the infant mortality rate.

Emefiene et al. (2025) studied the impact of maternal mortality on economic growth in Nigeria using secondary data from the World Development Indicators and UNESCO Institute for Statistics. The study employed a multiple regression analysis model to assess the impact of maternal mortality and other economic variables on Nigeria's GDP. The results showed that the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) and capital stock (k) negatively correlated with GDP. While capital stock (k) significantly affects GDP, MMR is insignificant. The result further revealed that variables such as education, exports, and arable land showed a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with GDP at the 5% significant level.

Soharwardi (2020) studied the role of mother empowerment and macro-economic factors for child health: an evidence from developing economies. Maternal empowerment was measured through five dimensions: work status, awareness, decision making, self-esteem, and self-confidence. On the other hand, countries' net food imports, countries as secular or nonsecular and religion were selected as macro-economic factors. Data was analyzed through the use of binary logistic regression and explored the impact of maternal empowerment and macro-economic factors on child health. Results revealed the positive impact of mother empowerment in the improvement of child health. Results further revealed that net food imports are positively affecting the child's health. Most probably, the more empowered mothers were more contributors and implement positive effects on their children's health. Yeboah et al. (2025) studied the impact of economic growth and recession on maternal and child health outcomes in sub-Saharan African

countries: a systematic literature review. A structured search of Medline, Embase, Web of Science, EconLit, and Global Health was conducted. Inclusion criteria encompassed studies published between 2000 to 2022 that examined national level growth and recession in conjunction with health outcomes of mothers and children in sub-Saharan African countries. Results showed that a total of 1167 studies were initially identified from the database searches, of which 18 met the inclusion criteria for data extraction. The review presented a range of findings. Eleven studies underscore the significant impact of economic growth in reducing child mortality and under nutrition, and maternal mortality rate. Conversely, other studies indicated insignificant or inconsistent associations, emphasizing the importance of various socio-economic factors such as female education, equitable resource distribution, effective governance, and comprehensive maternal and child health coverage and interventions.

Salvatore (2023) carried out a study on investing in maternal health: economic benefits and policy implications. The study explores the economic impact of maternal health, including its effects on human capital, productivity and healthcare costs. The study emphasized the importance of addressing social determinants such as access to healthcare services, education, employment, income and geographical disparities. The findings revealed that prioritizing maternal health bears profound economic implications, as women's access to and utilization of maternal healthcare services directly impact their productivity and economic engagement. The result further revealed that in low-and middle-income countries, each dollar invested in material health interventions yielded returns of up to \$16 in improved health and productivity outcomes. Additionally, the results revealed that investing in material health contributes to poverty reduction (see United Nations Population Fund, 2017).

Souza et al. (2024) studied a global analysis of the determinants of maternal health and transitions in maternal mortality. The paper analyzed the distal and proximal determinants of maternal health, as well as the exposures, risk factors, and micro-correlates related to maternal mortality. The paper conducted two systematic reviews of the literature; and also analyzed publicly available data on indicators related to the Sustainable Development Goals, specifically, estimates prepared by international organizations including the UN and the World Bank. The paper revealed that preventable deaths of millions of women each decade are not solely due to biomedical complications of pregnancy, childbirth, and the postnatal period, but are also tangible manifestations of the prevailing determinants of maternal health and persistent inequities in global health and socioeconomic development.

Anumudu et al. (2025) studied a global review of maternal mortality, its health determinants, and factors that influence care utilization in women of child-bearing years in Nigeria. The review specifically addresses the difficulties faced in assessing medical care, and the ongoing initiatives to lower the maternal mortality ratio. Primary studies (published after year 2000) focused on maternal mortality, health determinants, and the utilization of maternal healthcare services in Nigeria were retrieved following a systematic search across multiple databases, including Scopus, PubMed, Google Scholar, and web of Science. These were screened using defined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Results revealed that a total of 21 publications were

included in the review comprising 2 qualitative, 17 quantitative, and 2 mixed study designs. Major health determinants identified in these studies include hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, hemorrhage, and sepsis/septicaemia, contributing as much as 29%, 24%, and 14.2% of maternal deaths respectively in over 10% of the reviewed studies. The results further revealed that socio-economic determinants including poverty, maternal education, health systems issues and culture significantly impacted the utilization of maternal healthcare services, inadvertently impacting maternal mortality.

Wheelock (2023) carried out a study on “our mothers are dying”: How economics affect maternal mortality. The aim of the thesis was to give qualitative and quantitative backing to a deeper investigation of the correlation between economic success and maternal health. This study focused on some European countries, from the years 2000 – 2017. The study used GDP per capita, the GINI coefficient, and the Economic Freedom Index to measure the independent variables. The three variables are measures of economic success. Maternal mortality was used to measure the dependent variable. The data for the study was analyzed using a time series case study, regression analysis. Time series panel analysis was also used in the study. Results show a strong correlation between maternal mortality and the Economic Freedom Index. GDP per capita does not have a strong correlation with maternal mortality in the pool of European Countries.

Methodology

This paper adopted the ex-post facto research design. The choice of the ex-post facto research design was informed by the fact that the numerical data required for the actual empirical analysis was collected from secondary sources.

Model Specification

Maternal Mortality Model

This capture objective three and adopted from the work of Salatin & Bidari (2014) and Bao et al (2022) but with some modification in terms of the variables.

$$MAM = f (INF, GDPPC, GEH, UNEMP) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) form of the equation is written as:

$$MAM = C_0 + C_1INF + C_2GDPPC + C_3GEH + C_4UNEMP + U \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$C_1 > 0; C_2 < 0; C_3 < 0; C_4 > 0$$

Where;

- MAM = Material mortality rate
- INF = Inflation rate
- GDPPC = GDP per capita
- GEH = Government Expenditure on Health

UNEMP = Unemployment rate

C₀ = constant

C₁- C₄ = Coefficient of explanatory variables

U = error term

Estimation Technique

This study employed descriptive statistics, unit root test, Co-integration, and Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) modelling techniques to estimate the effect of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable.

Result and Discussions

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 below presents the result of the descriptive statistics of the variables employed in the estimations in this study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics Test Results

	MAM	INF	GDPPC	GEH	UNEMP
Mean	1127.467	18.33257	317609.4	143.2849	14.34000
Median	1124.000	13.01000	226245.0	81.91000	13.90000
Maximum	1285.000	72.84000	1028712.	468.6400	27.40000
Minimum	993.0000	5.390000	5093.070	0.150000	3.500000
Std. Dev.	70.17972	15.66996	308578.0	155.5025	7.699054
Skewness	0.324039	2.200667	0.766491	0.838774	-0.125980
Kurtosis	2.791545	7.021038	2.391439	2.303994	1.681559
Jarque-Bera	0.675877	51.82987	3.967222	4.810445	2.627582
Probability	0.713239	0.000000	0.137572	0.090245	0.268799
Sum	39461.33	641.6400	11116329	5014.970	501.9000
Sum Sq. Dev.	167456.5	8348.623	3.24E+12	822155.3	2015.365
Observations	35	35	35	35	35

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

The result of the descriptive statistics in Tables 1 shows that maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) has a mean value of 1127.467 with a standard deviation of 70.17972. The skewness value of Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) is positive (0.324039), meaning that Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) has a long-left while the kurtosis value of Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) is 2.791545 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

Inflation (INF) has a mean value of 18.33257 with a standard deviation of 15.66996. The skewness value of Inflation (INF) is negative (2.200667), meaning that Inflation (INF) has a long-left tail while the kurtosis

value of Inflation (INF) is 7.021038 (i. e. greater than 3), meaning that it is leptokurtic. That is, it has a peak distribution, meaning that the series has more value higher than the sample mean.

Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a mean value of 317609.4 with a standard deviation of 308578.0. The skewness value of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) is positive (0.766491), meaning that Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a longright tail while the kurtosis value of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) is 2.391439 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a mean value of 143.2849 with a standard deviation of 155.5025. The skewness value of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) is positive (0.838774), meaning that Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) is 2.303994 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

While Unemployment (UNEMP) has a mean value of 14.34000 with a standard deviation of 7.699054. The skewness value of Unemployment (UNEMP) is negative (-0.125980), meaning that Unemployment (UNEMP) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Unemployment (UNEMP) is 1.681559 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series has low value lower than the sample mean.

Again, one important observation in this table is the Jarque-Bera statistics of the variables. It shows that the values of INF is greater than 5.99, meaning that they do not have a normal distribution while UFM, LEXP, MAM, GDPPC, GEH and UNEMP has a value less than 5.99, suggesting that they have a normal distribution.

Based on these observations, it is therefore necessary to test for the stationarity of the variables and the long run relationship since using the variables at level might give a spurious result. The unit root test is conducted so as to make the variables stationary. The study adopts the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test procedure.

Unit Root Test for Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) Model

Tables 2 below presents the result of stationarity test for each of variables used using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results for Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM)Model

Variables	ADF at Level	ADF at 1st Difference	Status	Remarks
MAM	-1.892096	-5.938096	I(1)	Stationary
INF	-2.237259	-4.760123	I(1)	Stationary
GDPPC	1.075593	-7.303771	I(1)	Stationary
GEH	0.326534	-6.316342	I(1)	Stationary
UNEMP	-2.139660	-5.054909	I(1)	Stationary

Critical Values				
1% level	-3.646342	-3.653730		
5% level	-2.954021	-2.957110		
10% level	-2.615817	-2.617434		

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The outcome of unit root test in Table 2 for the Model, revealed that all the variables were not stationary at level but were stationary at difference. Hence, this study concludes that the variables used in model were integrated of order one, that is I (1). Since the ADF results indicate that the series are of the same order of integration, we proceed to conduct co-integration.

(ii) Co-integration Test Result for Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) Model

The result of co-integration test for Model is presented in Table 3 below. This will enable us determine if there exists long run equilibrium relationship among variables applied in this model.

Table 3: Co-integration Test Result for Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) Model.

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized	Trace	0.05	Prob.**
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value
None *	0.740990	105.0389	69.81889
At most 1 *	0.673655	60.45953	47.85613
At most 2	0.383323	23.50616	29.79707
At most 3	0.187529	7.553648	15.49471
At most 4	0.020999	0.700359	3.841465

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Max-eigenvalue)

Hypothesized	Max-Eigen	0.05	Prob.**
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value
None *	0.740990	44.57935	33.87687
At most 1 *	0.673655	36.95337	27.58434
At most 2	0.383323	15.95251	21.13162
At most 3	0.187529	6.853289	14.26460

At most 4 0.020999 0.700359 3.841465 0.4027

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

The co-integration outcomes in Table 3 above reveals that both the trace test statistics and the max-eigenvalue statistics indicate two (2) co-integrating equation at 5 % significance level.

This suggests that there exists a long-run relationship among variables in the model. Accordingly, the study rejects the null hypothesis of no co-integration amongst the variables but accepts the alternative hypothesis.

(ii) Over-Parameterized ECM Estimation Results for Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) Model

The result of over-parametrized ECM estimation of the Model is presented in equation 4 below.

Table 4: Over-parameterized ECM Estimation Results for Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) Model

Dependent Variable: DLOG(MAM)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/29/25 Time: 00:32

Sample (adjusted): 1993 2024

Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.001678	0.004741	-0.353972	0.7280
DLOG(MAM(-1))	0.507207	0.190214	2.666509	0.0169
DLOG(MAM(-2))	0.366835	0.206804	1.773835	0.0951
D(INF)	-6.58E-05	0.000343	-0.191860	0.8503
D(INF(-1))	0.000928	0.000264	3.511631	0.0029
D(INF(-2))	-7.56E-06	0.000208	-0.036292	0.9715
DLOG(GDPPC)	-0.085253	0.027185	-3.136025	0.0064
DLOG(GDPPC(-1))	-0.024218	0.031410	-0.771031	0.4519
DLOG(GDPPC(-2))	0.095342	0.029807	3.198674	0.0056
DLOG(GEH)	-0.005293	0.006025	-0.878380	0.3927
DLOG(GEH(-1))	0.006773	0.006148	1.101606	0.2869
DLOG(GEH(-2))	0.011095	0.006051	1.833657	0.0854
D(UNEMP)	-0.000458	0.000553	-0.827591	0.4201
D(UNEMP(-1))	-0.000269	0.000491	-0.546905	0.5920
D(UNEMP(-2))	0.000891	0.000525	1.698018	0.1089

ECM(-1)	-0.311731	0.093225	-3.343863	0.0041
R-squared	0.786978	Mean dependent var		-0.006305
Adjusted R-squared	0.587270	S.D. dependent var		0.016051
S.E. of regression	0.010312	Akaike info criterion		-6.004223
Sum squared resid	0.001701	Schwarz criterion		-5.271355
Log likelihood	112.0676	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-5.761298
F-statistic	3.940638	Durbin-Watson stat		1.915041
Prob(F-statistic)	0.004870			

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

(iii) Parsimonious ECM of the Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) Model The result of ECM estimation of the Model is obtainable in table5 below.

Table 5: Parsimonious ECM Estimation Results for Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) Model)

Dependent Variable: DLOG(MAM)

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/29/25 Time: 00:34

Sample (adjusted): 1993 2024

Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.003627	0.003413	-1.062830	0.2999
DLOG(MAM(-1))	0.535732	0.160591	3.336015	0.0031
DLOG(MAM(-2))	0.334623	0.179986	1.859159	0.0771
D(INF(-1))	0.000868	0.000230	3.774235	0.0011
DLOG(GDPPC)	-0.086435	0.024400	-3.542479	0.0019
DLOG(GDPPC(-2))	0.091554	0.021759	4.207729	0.0004
DLOG(GEH)	-0.007883	0.004148	-1.900160	0.0712
DLOG(GEH(-1))	0.004199	0.004453	0.942844	0.3565
DLOG(GEH(-2))	0.009089	0.004158	2.185984	0.0403
D(UNEMP(-2))	0.001002	0.000412	2.431314	0.0241
ECM(-1)	-0.431449	0.138226	-3.121340	0.0038
R-squared	0.762004	Mean dependent var		-0.006305
Adjusted R-squared	0.648673	S.D. dependent var		0.016051
S.E. of regression	0.009514	Akaike info criterion		-6.205865
Sum squared resid	0.001901	Schwarz criterion		-5.702018

Log likelihood	110.2938	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-6.038854
F-statistic	6.723678	Durbin-Watson stat	2.115481
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000126		

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

From Table 5, it shows that the explanatory variables included in the model explained about 65 percent of variation in poverty in Nigeria as shown by Adjusted-R² of 0.648673, the remaining 35 percent is explained by the error term. The F-statistic of 6.723678 with a prob. Value of 0.000126 shows that the model is statistically significant and that independent variables are significant explanatory factors of the dependent variable. The above implies that model has a goodness of fit and Durbin Watson Statistic of 2.115481 reveals that there is minimal serial autocorrelation among variables used in model. Also, the Error correction coefficient (ECM) is statistically significant and appropriately signed. This reveals that secondary school enrolment in Nigeria adjust to changes in explanatory variables by about 43 per cent annually.

Furthermore, From Table 5, the result of the short run estimation shows that Inflation (INF) has a positive (0.000868) relationship with Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM), suggesting that a unit increase in Inflation (INF) increases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) by 0.000868 units in Nigeria. The positive effect of Inflation (INF) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) confirm to a priori and therefore is line with economic theory. The coefficient of Inflation (INF) is statistically significant at 5 percent level in the short run. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Inflation (INF) and Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) but do not reject the alternative hypothesis in the short run.

Both current and past lag 2 of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a negative (0.086435 and -0.091554, respectively) relationship with Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM), suggesting that a unit increase in Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) reduces Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in Nigeria. The negative effect of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) conform to a priori and therefore is in line with economic theory. The negative effect of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) and Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis.

Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a negative (-0.007883) relationship with Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM), suggesting that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) decreases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) by 0.007883 units in Nigeria.

The negative sign of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) confirm to a priori and therefore is in line with economic theory. The negative sign of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) is

statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) and Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis.

While Unemployment (UNEMP) has a positive (0.001002) relationship with Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM), suggesting that a unit increase in Unemployment (UNEMP) increases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) by 0.001002 units in Nigeria. The positive sign of Unemployment (UNEMP) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) confirm to a priori and therefore is in line with economic theory. The positive sign of Unemployment (UNEMP) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Unemployment (UNEMP) and Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis.

(v) Post Estimation Test for the Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) Model

The researcher conducted a diagnostic test to determine whether or not series were free from order autocorrelation (Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test) and heteroscedasticity (Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test).

The outcome of the diagnostic tests is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Ramsey Reset Test, Serial Correlation LM Test and Homoscedasticity Test Results for Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) Model

	F-Statistic	Prob. Value
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	1.787369	0.1944
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test	1.224262	0.3318

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

From Table 6, the outcome of autocorrelation test using Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM method showed F-statistics is 1.787369 with a Chi-Square probability value is 0.1944.

This indicated that probability value of about 19 percent (0.1944) is larger than 5 percent (0.05) critical value; hence confirmed no serial correlation in model.

Again, result of heteroscedasticity test using Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test showed the Fstatistics is 1.224262 and a Chi-Square probability value is 0.3318. This suggested no evidence of heteroskedasticity in model since Chi-square probability value of about 33 percent is more than 5 percent ($p > 0.05$). So, residuals do have constant variance which is desirable in regression denoting that residual are Homoscedastic.

Discussions

Inflation and Maternal Mortality Rate in Nigeria

The study revealed that Inflation (INF) has a positive relationship with Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM). This means that a percentage increase in Inflation (INF) increases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review. The

coefficient of Inflation (INF) is statistically significant at 5 percent level in the short run. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Inflation (INF) and Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) but do not reject the alternative hypothesis in the short run. This means that Inflation (INF) significantly increases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in Nigeria.

The positive findings of this study supports previous studies like Mostert (2023) who found out that declining economic state worsens maternal and mental health outcomes.

GDP per capita and Maternal Mortality Rate in Nigeria

The study revealed that Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) has a negative relationship with Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM). This means that a unit increase in Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) reduces Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review.

The negative effect of Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) and Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis. This means that Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPPC) significantly reduces Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in Nigeria.

The negative findings of this study agrees with the work of Wheelock (2023) who found out that GDP per capita do not have a strong correlation with maternal mortality in the pool of European countries.

Government Expenditure on Health and Maternal Mortality Rate in Nigeria

The study revealed that Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) has a negative relationship with Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM). This means that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) decreases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in

Nigeria in the short run within the period under review. The negative sign of Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) and Maternal Mortality Rate

(MAM) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis. This means that Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) significantly reduces Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in Nigeria.

The negative findings of this study is in line with Adegoke et al.(2022) who found a significant negative relationship between total health expenditure and maternal mortality rate but contrasts with the work of Okeowo et al.(2025) who found out that health expenditure has a positive relationship with maternal mortality.

Unemployment and Maternal Mortality Rate in Nigeria

The study revealed that Unemployment (UNEMP) has a positive relationship with Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM). This means that a percentage increase in Unemployment (UNEMP) rate increases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in Nigeria in the short run within the period under review. The positive sign of

Unemployment (UNEMP) on Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Unemployment (UNEMP) and Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in the short run but do not reject the alternative hypothesis. This means that Unemployment (UNEMP) significantly increases Maternal Mortality Rate (MAM) in Nigeria.

The positive findings of this study agrees with the work of Adegoke et al, (2022) who found out that a significant positive relationship exist between maternal mortality and unemployment.

Concluding Remarks

The results of the ECM shows that Inflation (INF) reduces maternal mortality rate; GDP per capitareduces maternal mortality rate; Government Expenditure on Health (GEH) reduces maternal mortality rate; and Unemployment (UNEMP) increases maternal mortality rate in Nigeria during the period of study.

Thus, to avoid maternal deaths, it is vital to prevent unintended pregnancies. All women, including adolescents, need access to contraception, safe abortion services to the full extent of the law, and quality post-abortion care. Most maternal deaths are preventable, as the healthcare solutions to prevent or manage complications are well known. All women need access to high quality care in pregnancy, and during and after childbirth. Maternal health and newborn health are closely linked.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. In order to improve maternal health and consequently reduce maternal mortality in Nigeria, governments are required to initiate and implement effective macroeconomic policies aimed at controlling inflation in order to safeguard household consumption of essential goods and health services, thereby reducing inflation-induced maternal mortality.
2. Policies aimed at boosting GDP per capital, increasing health care expenditure and addressing unemployment especially among women is vital for enhancing maternal health in Nigeria.
3. Empowering women through access to education and relevant skills is sin qua non to improving maternal health thereby reducing maternal mortality rate in Nigeria.
4. Fiscal and monetary policy measures aimed at stabilizing prices and reducing unemployment rate should be prioritized by the government having known its significance on maternal health in Nigeria.

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